

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF ENGLISH AND UZBEK PROVERBS EXPRESSING LOVE

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Abstract: This article deals with the features of proverbs in languages of different structures with component “love” in cultural linguistics. It presents the proverbs in English and Uzbek languages, which reflect the national consciousness, value, morality and wisdom of these peoples. There is classification and analysis of paremiological units with the component “love” that help to identify the unique units of proverbs for both languages in the article.

Keywords: concept, linguoculture, culture, paremiology, proverbs.

Language is one of the means of access to human consciousness, its conceptosphere, to the content and structure of concepts as units of thinking. Language does not exist outside of culture as a “socially inherited set of practical skills and ideas that characterize our way of life” [3]. As one of the types of human activity, language is an integral part of culture, defined as a combination of the results of human activity in different spheres of human life: industrial, social, spiritual.

V. A. Maslova points out the following objects of cultural linguistics: first of all there are words and phrases, which have no equivalents in another language; then: archetypes, rituals, beliefs, and superstitions reflected in a language; on the third place there are proverbs and sayings; idioms; symbols and stereotypes; metaphors and images; end the list stylistic of norms and speech behavior [2].

Culture is always accompanied by certain concepts that help people of the same culture, and sometimes even of different cultures. Concepts are abstract units that reflect the content of acquired knowledge, experience, results of all human activities and the results of cognition of the surrounding world in the form of certain units.

Representatives of cognitive linguistics in linguistics define the concept as a unit of operational significance. Ye.S. Kubryakova describes it as follows: “The concept is operational meaningful unit of memory, mental lexicon, conceptual system and language of the brain (lingua mentalis), the whole picture of the world reflected in the human psyche”[1]. Therefore, according to the aforementioned approach, the concept is a meaningful cognitive unit that reflects the knowledge of the surrounding world in the human mind.

The concept of “Love” is one of the central concepts in any culture. The phenomenon of love is unique. No concept encompasses such a range of meanings as “Love”. The study of the concept of “Love” in various cultural and linguistic communities contributes to international understanding by relating its sociocultural behavioral stereotypes with the stereotypes of people from other cultures.

The specificity of concepts in different languages is determined by cultural traditions, historically enshrined value orientations, adopted in the corresponding linguistic culture. In

each culture, love is interpreted differently. It depends on the national specifics and understanding of the very concept of "Love". The value component of the concept "Love" is a set of evaluation characteristics of the concepts, reflecting both universal and ethno-specific values. The universal values reflected in the linguistic consciousness include: life, health, happiness, pleasure, beauty, glory, and others. These concepts are often associated with the concept of "Love".

One of the ways of investigating the concept can be presented by the method of analysis of the proverbs. The proverb is a complex unit of a language reflecting human life experiences and practice, his attitude towards society, history, culture, mentality, ethic and esthetical senses, positive and negative characters.

Paremiology is at the intersection of phraseology and folklore, which makes the study of proverbs and sayings very significant from the perspective of the modern linguocultural approach. The paremiological foundation of language is an important source of interpretation.

Love is a truly vast domain, and certainly an area that inspired a lot of proverbial wisdom. It is no wonder that there are so many proverbs about love in both languages under study. Although "Love" is a universal concept, it has its own peculiarities in each culture. In addition, to understand more the attitude of English people to love, we have analyzed love proverbs, which contain the evaluation of people to this feeling.

On the basis of the English love proverbs, we assume that for English people:

1. Love overcomes all obstacles; nothing and nobody can resist it. Love provides a stimulus to forgive, trust, worry about the destiny of the loved one; love transforms a person. It is impossible to hide love. These ideas are proved by such proverbs as: *Love knows no boundaries; Love makes all burdens light; Love conquers all; Love makes the world go round; Love makes all men equal; love rules his kingdom without a sword.*[4]

2. An important place in English paremiological units is the idea that love can bring not only joy and happiness, but also pain and suffering: *Great love, great sorrow; Love is full of fear; Love's beginning is fear, middle sin, and end grief and annoyance; There is no living in love without suffering; The love of ladies causes pain to lovers and death to horses.*

3. Loving people lose the ability to watch things sensibly. In other words, when you are in love with someone, you may refuse to see anything bad about that person. For example, *Love is blind; Love sees no faults; Love your friend with his fault.*

4. Love depends on a number of circumstances, such as money. The factual material indicates that in the English linguistic consciousness there is a thought that money is more important for a person than feelings, and that without money there is no love: *When the poverty comes in at the door, love flies out of the window; Love lasts as long as money endures; Money is the sinews of love as well as of war; Who marries for love without money, has good nights and sorry days.*

However, a number of English phraseological units claim the opposite: *Love in a cottage; Love lives in cottages as well as in courts; Lovers live by love as larks live by leeks.*

5. Choosing an object of love is unmotivated, but at the same time the internal, intuitive motive of the choice is evaluated positively. We may prove these words with the help of the following proverbs: *Love and knowledge live not together; Love is without reason; Love is without law; Love needs no teaching.*

6. In some proverbs, we can assume the meaning that love is important in marriage while in others marriage is fatal for love. The following proverbs proves this conclusion: *Marry first, and love will follow; Where there's marriage without love, there will be love without marriage; It is unlucky to marry for love*

7. Love can be achieved by all means: *All is fair in love and war; all strategies are fair in love*. It means that anything you do in a relationship or in battle is acceptable.

8. Love is present in family relationships. Love between family members is an important aspect of love. It can be proved by such proverbs as: *A mother's love never ages; A mother's love is best of all; He that loves the tree loves the branch*.

In Uzbek linguistics Berdiyrov and Rasulov, Sodikova, Sh.Rahmatullaev, Sh. Shomaqsudov, Sh.Shorahmedov, Karomatov and Karomatova, T.Mirzayev, A.Musoqulov, B. Sarimsoqov, Mirzo , Ibrohim, Abdusamatov and Hamidkhonova, Madayev and some other scientists worked on proverbial research and created several dictionaries of proverbs. Such kind of works are being continued nowadays, too.

The Uzbek language is rich in proverbs and they are often poetic. The concept of love in Uzbek is expressed by the synonym words: “muhabbat”, “sevgi”, “ishq”. In Uzbek proverbs and sayings the following signs of concept “love” can be highlighted:

1. Love as an irrational sense. Uzbek proverbs provide evidence that love is an irrational feeling. There are proverbs and sayings, which emphasize the lack of control and unmotivated choice of the object of love. The beloved is not chosen according to certain criteria, he is perceived as he is. It can be proven with following proverbs in Uzbek: *Muhabbatning ko'zi – ko'r; Sevgining ko'zi ayb ko'rmas*. [5]

There are also proverbs with the meaning that the material beauty is not the main factor in choosing the object of love. For example, *Muhabbat chiroy tanlamas, uyqu – joy; Muhabbat husn tanlamas, uyqu – o'rin*.

2. In Uzbek proverbs love is equated with a disease whose symptoms are pronounced, obvious, despite the depth and power of love, it can not be overcome: *Hamma dardga bor davo, oshiqlik dardi – bedavo; Har kim beyordir – bemordir; Davosiz dard – muhabbat*.

It should be noted that in English paremiology it is possible to find their equivalent: No herb will cure love

3. Love is like a feeling that is not dependent on material well-being. In the following examples love is described as priceless, blessing that can not be acquired for any money: *Sof sevgi sotilmas, yo kesakdek otulmas; Sevgi bozorda sotilmas; Sevgi pulga sotilmas, ko'ngil pulga topilmas; Muhabbat boylikka boqmas*.

Undoubtedly, proverbs help to understand culture better. Some Uzbek proverbs may not have their equivalents in the English language as the proverbs: *Ishqi yo`q – eshak, dardi yo`q – kesak*. Love is a wide-ranging notion that the essence of this proverb is that a person who does not really care about any kind of work, profession, or anything is indifferent to everything like a donkey without any trouble except its stomach, and is like a motionless stone without any pain.

In the following proverb we can understand that in Uzbek culture the concept “love” does not only mean a love for a beloved one but also a love for the Homeland, the people, the family, parents, children, life. *Ishq demak – dunyoni sevmoq* (Love means to love the world). This proverb tells us to love the world and the things which surround us. [6]

In conclusion, it can be said that proverbs give insight into culture and customs of a nation and love has different characteristics in English and Uzbek but at the same time they have a lot of in common. In the proverbs of the Uzbek language, love is represented as a serious feeling that can be a source of happiness or unhappiness, it is unpredictable, controversial, brings suffering, but at the same time it is also a pleasure, it can be endured for it. An analysis of the English proverbs shows that love is a strong emotion, which is an integral part of a person's life; it can overcome any obstacles. Love is selfless, but at the same time it can be mercenary. All in all, Love is the highest power as it is priceless.

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